

Personality Issues in Existential Psychology

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Annotation: This article presents scientific reflections on the concept of existentialism, its goals and objectives, the research of existentialist scientists, the existential crisis.

Keywords: existentialism, logotherapy, meaning of life, object, subject, existential psychotherapy.

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At the heart of the reforms carried out in our country today, it is important to shape a socially healthy environment, develop impressive mechanisms of youth education, spiritual maturation of the individual, psychological illumination of these fields, while the ideas of a perfect person stand out. At this point, research on the work of the directions of modern psychology aimed at the problem of personality formation and development. The successful cooperation of the individual and his in relations with society, the spiritual perfection of the individual, the search for an adequate solution in various life difficulties and crises and the development of the skills of being able to find. In psychology, there are several theories aimed at studying personality issues, each theory approaches this problem on the subject of research. In particular, existential theory in psychology has its own approach method, on the basis of this concept the meaning of an individual's life stands.

Existential direction originated in Europe in the first half of the 20th century, with the likes of Karl Yaspers, Ludwig Binswanger, Medard Boss, Victor Frankl contributing immensely to the development of the direction. Existential psychology is the cohesion of psychology, the direction in which a certain person's life arises according to the philosophy of existentialism, which can not be reduced to general schemes, arising from its uniqueness.

The concept of "existentialism" means "emergence", "emergence", "formation". In it, a person plays a fundamental role not as a static set of psychodynamic mechanics, a form of behavior, natural and personal qualities, but as a being that always exists and divides. The existential psychology approach to psychology was introduced by the German philosopher and psychologist Karl Yaspers, whose works such as "general psychology", "the importance and content of history" are aimed at revising the existing methodologies and approaches in psychiatry.

Existential psychology studies the following issues:

1. Death challenges life and time;
2. Problems of freedom of choice and responsibility;
3. Loneliness, intuition and communication problems;
4. Problems of searching for content of existence;

The main subject of Existential Psychology - the meaning of human life, the study of the conditions for its transformation, loss and achievement - is presented in many literature. One of the

central concepts of existentialism is considered to be existentialism, where existentialism is the indivisibility, indivisibility of a human borlig object and subect whole.

- Existentialism is the human “I” who makes a person discover his own private inner world, independent, rather than through a preemptive plan. As ideas of Existential Psychology,
- the following are cited:
- The free will of a person helps him to be in constant development;
- Knowledge of one's own inner world is the basic need of the individual;
- Realizing one's own death and accepting that fact is a powerful resource to unlock the creativity that exists in the individual.

The principles of existentialism are reflected in:

1. In accordance with man, his existence precedes his essence. A person makes himself a person.
 2. Human being is a way of living freely. Freedom is not” freedom of spirit“, it is”freedom of choice”.
 3. The existence of a person encompasses responsibility to himself: not only for himself, but for those around him, the world interposed on freedom is whole: without deciding how to act, a person chooses to be a person of one or another nature, both to life and to himself.
 4. Temporary and completed existence. Human existence is a being that appeals to death.
- According to the existential psychologist and psychotherapist Rollo Mei: a person is responsible for his own existence. When a person wants to be the original self , he must realize himself and be responsible for himself. Existential analysts identify 3 modes of the world (simultaneous tamons) :
 - The surrounding world - the material-the “biological” and” physical” world, the human being is surrounded by the external environment, the world of objects.
 - The inner world is the world of beings of the same species, the world of people close to man, the world of relations between people, which changes during them.
 - O'doniyosi - the world of self-awareness and self-determination, the world”for myself”.

Such an understanding of the world is one of the main ideas of Existential Psychology that in many cases it happens at the cost of choosing one world, losing another. Schwetzarian psychathers Ludwig Binswanger and Medard boss developed O'conception based on the existential theory of the German philosopher Martin Heidegger. L. Binsvanger:”existential analysis does not offer an ontological thesis about fundamental conditions in a defined being, it does not give an exact data present in the realism inherent to the configuration and form of existentialism”. M. From Shvetsaria.Boss's work:” introduction to Psychosomatic Medicine“,” analysis of Dreams”,”psychoanalysis and Daisen analysis”. These works are aimed at developing the basis of a new existential therapy. Binswanger and Boss believe that there is no causal relationship in human life. There is essentially a sequence of behavior that cannot elicit causality through this sequence. These researchers have a negative attitude to any psychological theory, under the zero theory there is always one hypothesis or another, and for these scientists, phenomena felt from the human side, experienced and realized by it are real, not scientific hypotheses. The fundamental concept of the Binswanger and Boss concept is” presence in the world ” (Dasein). In their opinion, the world of human existence has 3 levels:

1. Human environment;
2. Man himself, his body.
3. Biological or physical environment;

In Psychology, V. Frankl created the theory of existential analysis and logotherapy that takes on the nature of Man, the mechanisms of the normal development of the individual and pathology (abnormality), a complex system of medical, philosophical and psychological views that has a way and method of improving anomalies in the development of the individual. V. According to Frankl, in order to humanize the meaning and meaning of human life, it is necessary for people to have a good understanding of their responsibilities to humanity. A "good man" is not a "neurotic person", nor a disruptive conformist, but an individual, a more reflective, confident man who discovers a newness, with the necessary knowledge to conduct such experiments. Logotherapy V. Is a psychotherapeutic approach developed by Frankl. The driving force of logotherapy is the idea that motivates people the most in their search for meaning, which indicates that the meaning of life is the greatest question in our mind and the greatest stress in our psyche. Logotherapy (Greek logos - speech, speech and therapeia - care, treatment) –one of the directions of psychotherapy, aimed at studying the meaningful properties of existence and helping to seek and understand the meaning and essence of life, which has a good therapeutic effect. Then, based on the above analyzes, using the directions of psychological influence when dealing with personality issues, an existential orientation approach to the issue of understanding the meaning of human life will help to look at the problem of personality from the point of view of the meaning of his life and will serve to develop the skills of understanding and content.

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